

Description of scurvy by Eichtius (1541)

Summary by James Lind (1753)

In the 16th century, four European authors described the symptoms of scurvy in such a detail that the disease can be recognized as the disease we currently classify as scurvy: *Eichtius* (1541), *Olaus Magnus* (1555), *Ronsseus* (1564), and *Wierus* (1567). Since these four texts are among the early unambiguous descriptions of scurvy, they have substantial historical relevance. All these texts were originally published in Latin. There are English translations of the sections of scurvy from the Olaus Magnus text. James Lind wrote English summaries of the texts of the three other authors. This document gives a brief background and a copy of Lind's summary of Eichtius (1541) text on scurvy.

Various names of the author (1515–1576):

Eichtius

Johannes Eichtius

Jan Echt

Johann Bachoven von Echt

<https://doi.org/10.31952/amha.16.2.2>

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/30488702>

<https://zenodo.org/records/14296049>

Yellow is used to indicate the description of symptoms of scurvy.

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Background

James Lind (1753)¹ wrote, p.1

In the first accounts given us of this disease, by *Ronsseus*², *Echthius*³, and *Wierus*⁴ (a), it is surprising to find, not only an accurate description of it, but an enumeration of almost all the truly antiscorbutic medicines that are known to the world even at this day.

(a) The first authors on the scurvy, *Ronsseus* and *Echthius*, though cotemporary, wrote separately, without having the benefit of seeing each others works.

James Lind p.2

Echthius seems to be the first who gave rise to the opinion of its being a contagious or infectious *lues*. He was led into that mistake, by observing whole monasteries who lived on the same diet, and in the same air, at once affected with it, especially after fevers; which no doubt might become infectious in close and confined apartments. He imagined, therefore, that a scurvy might in a manner be the *crisis* of a fever, which as such he deemed contagious.

James Lind p.36

[About *Thomas Willis*] Had he taken the first method he mentions, and described the symptoms proper and peculiar to this disease alone, as *Echthius* has done; — or the second method, that of describing it in its beginning, progress, and different stages, as the first and purest writers have all done; he

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- 1 James Lind (1753). A Treatise of the Scurvy in Three Parts. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10685194> Selected sections of Lind's treatise. Lind's 1753 edition in a scanned versions: <https://wellcomecollection.org/works/bg2gxrzz/items?canvas=7> <https://archive.org/details/treatisescurvyt00lind/page/xvi/mode/2up> <https://library.si.edu/digital-library/book/treatisescurvyt00lind>
 - 2 Ronsseus, see: Lind. Part III: Chapter II. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17093314> <https://archive.org/details/treatisescurvyt00lind/page/356/mode/2up>
 - 3 Echthius, see: Lind. Part III: Chapter II. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17093279> <https://archive.org/details/treatisescurvyt00lind/page/354/mode/2up>
 - 4 Wierus, see: Lind. Part III: Chapter II. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17093229> <https://archive.org/details/treatisescurvyt00lind/page/358/mode/2up>

might have given us some light into the matter.

James Lind p.52

[About *Willis*] But it will appear to any person who peruses the authors from whom he has borrowed the description of the symptoms, viz. *Echthius*, *Wierus*, &c. that they described a very different disease from what *Willis* did. Dr *Willis*'s method of cure may perhaps be rationally applied to the diseases he described; but is by no means adapted to the disease characterised by the first writers on the scurvy.

James Lind p.63

As to the pathognomonic signs of this disease: If we compare its symptoms as described by *Echthius*, *Wierus*, and all other authors till the time of *Eugalenus* (a), with the accounts given of them in books of voyages, particularly the extraordinary narrative of what happened to the great Lord *Anson*'s crews in their passage round the world (b), we shall perceive an entire agreement in the essential signs of the distemper, (making a proper allowance for the different descriptions that may be expected from seamen and physicians), and appearances so singular as are not to be met with in any other. Thus, putrid gums, swelled legs, and spots, accompanying each other, and in their progress usually attended with rigid tendons in the ham, are observed in no other distemper.

James Lind p.352-355

... The author afterwards observes it to be the scurvy, a malady to which the northern nations, the *Dutch*, &c. are very subject; and upon this occasion, quoting a passage from *Olaus Magnus*⁵, says, "I have delighted myself to recite the words of this author, because he speaketh thereof as being skilled, and has well described the disease; only he maketh no mention of the stiffening of the hams, nor of the superfluous flesh which groweth in the mouth."

...

5 Olaus Magnus (1555) *Historia de gentibus septentrionalibus*.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13380745> English translation of the sections on scurvy
https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/A_Description_of_the_Northern_Peoples
https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Olaus_Magnus

Olaus Magnus, in his history of the northern nations, published *ann.* 1555, observing what diseases are peculiar to them, gives us a long description of the scurvy.

...

Soon after we find three eminent physicians, all cotemporary, treating expressly of this distemper, *viz.*

Ronsseus, *Echthius*, and *Wierus*. To whom *Langius* may be added as a fourth, having wrote two epistles upon this subject. What is called *Echthius's Epitome*, was the first wrote, though the last published. It would appear from *Forrestus* to be a letter sent, in the year 1541, to *Blienburchius*, a physician at *Utrecht*; whose answer is now lost. The first book published expressly upon the scurvy was by *Ronsseus*, in the form of an epistle. The year is uncertain, as he afterwards corrected, and reprinted it in a different form. He is so modest as to say, that had he first seen *Wierus's* accurate observations, he would not have published any thing upon the subject. There is an edition of *Ronsseus* put down by *Mercklin* and *Lipenius*, in the year 1564; and of *Wierus's* observations in 1567. The learned Dr *Astruc* is of opinion, that these last were not published till 1580. It is thus far certain, that those authors corresponded together; and upon *Wierus* sending to *Ronsseus*, *Echthius's* letter, now called his *Epitome*, he published it, together with his own work, *Wierus's* observations, and two of *Langius's* epistles, in the year 1583.

James Lind p.445, Appendix

It has been no easy matter to obtain a knowledge of the many writings on this distemper. There have been collections made from time to time, of the several authors on the plague, venereal disease, &c. but no such have been compiled of writers on the scurvy. *Sennertus*, *ann.* 1624, when he wrote his own treatise, reprinted the writings of *Solomon Albertus* and *Martini*, together with *Ronsseus*, and the authors which he had published *ann.* 1583, *viz.* *Echthius*, *Wierus*, and *Langius*; and this book, containing those seven authors, is the only collection ever published of writers on the scurvy. There was here as little assistance to be obtained from medical *bibliothecæ*.

August Hirsch (1885)⁶ wrote, p.513

Of somewhat later date are the first authentic accounts of the epidemic occurrence of scurvy on land... Shortly after there appeared the statements of **Olaus Magnus**, concerning the often observed epidemic prevalence of scurvy in the Scandinavian kingdoms, especially in times of famine; and about the same time, or a little later, the writings of **Echthius**, **Ronsseus**, **Wier**, **Dodonaeus** and **Brucaeus**, which testify to the comparatively common occurrence of the disease along the littoral of the North Sea and the Baltic...

These excellent descriptions of the malady, more especially by **Echthius**, **Ronsseus** and **Wier**, leave no doubt as to its nature [as scurvy].

Alfred Hess (1920)⁷ wrote, p.1-4

It is probable that scurvy existed in the northern parts of Europe and Asia ever since they were settled by man. We should hardly expect to have records of this condition, in view of the low educational status of the people, their greatly restricted literature, and their lack of intercourse with the people in the southern countries. In the sixteenth century, with the development and spread of education, we begin to hear of scurvy from various sources. **Olaus Magnus**, in his "History of the Northern Nations," published in 1555, described the disease which he tells us flourished among the soldiers in the camps and in the prisons.

About this time **Ronsseus**, **Echthius** and **Wierus** wrote special treatises on this disease, and recommended many dietary measures which we recognize to-day as most efficacious. The number of monographs on this subject multiplied with great rapidity in the course of the next twenty-five or fifty years; none of them, however, added anything essential to our knowledge...

6 Hirsch A (1885) Handbook of Geographical and Historical Pathology. Vol. II. Scurvy: pp.507-568.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10104179> Section on scurvy separately
<https://archive.org/details/handbookofgeogra02hirsuoft/page/512/mode/2up>
https://archive.org/details/b28147455_0002/page/512/mode/2up
<https://archive.org/details/handbookofgeogra02unse/page/512/mode/2up>
<https://archive.org/details/handbookofgeogra02hirs/page/512/mode/2up>

7 Hess AF (1920) Scurvy: Past and Present.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10685195> Extracts relevant to the current context
<https://www.gutenberg.org/ebooks/40505>
<https://digital.library.cornell.edu/catalog/chla2903792>

Anthony J Lorenz (1953)⁸ wrote:

p.308

Lind makes the Dutch physician, **Balduin Ronsseus**, *facile princeps*⁹. Ronsseus¹⁰ suggests that cold damp air of the sea and the seashore is the principal cause of scurvy. His is the first book written expressly on scurvy and was published in 1564. A later edition of Ronsseus (1585) combined the *epistolae* of **Echthius**¹¹ and Langius as well as the *observatio* of Wierus as a sort of compendium of the current views on scurvy. Ronsseus also held to the theory of involvement of the spleen in scurvy. Both Ronsseus and Echthius, writing separately, interpreted Pliny's description of the disease, which afflicted the Roman army under Germanicus, as scurvy.

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Wier (Wierus) (1567)¹², copying Echthius, and Bruner (Brunerus) (1589), copying Wierus (adding only that leg pains preceded the actual onset of scurvy) well might have justified the subhead in Lind's preface *Dies Diem Docet*¹³, and the words:

“To know a disease and to cure it being the utmost essential things to be learned, I have, therefore, transcribed the symptoms and the cure of the scurvy from those authors where they do not entirely copy from each other. I hope such motives (truth, and good of mankind) will to the candid and to the most judicious be a sufficient apology for the liberties I have assumed”.

In re-reading the principal pre-Lind authors *seriatim* one observes the transitions from land to sea scurvy, or *purpura nautica*. One also sees the transition of the concept of scurvy as a winter epidemic among urban populations and its entity as a deficiency disease when studied in the isolation of the sailing ship when voyages of discovery increased in duration sufficient to permit complete deprivation of antiscorbutic stores.

8 <https://doi.org/10.1079/PNS19530062>

9 Facile princeps. Acknowledged leader.

10 Ronsseus, B. (1585). *De Magnis Hippocratis lienibits Plinique stomachace ac sceletyrbe, seu vulgo dicto scorbuto commentariolus. Accessere q'usdem epistolae quinque ejusdem argumenti, Joannis Echthii de scorbuto epitome, Joannis Wieri de scorbuto observatio. Joanna's Langii epistolae duae de scorbuto*. Wittenberg: C. Schleich.

11 Echthius, J. (1541). *De Scorbuto, vel Scorbutica Passione Epitome*. Cologne.

12 Wier (Wierus) J. (1567). *Medicarum Observationum Rararum Liber (I de Scorbuto)*. Basle: J. Oporinus.

13 Dies Diem Docet. The day teaches the day; one learns by experience.

The text on the following pages is the summary by Lind (1753, 1st ed.) p.355-356

<https://archive.org/details/treatisescurvyt00lind/page/354/mode/2up>

<https://wellcomecollection.org/works/bg2gxrzz/items?canvas=377>

Jo. Echthius, a physician at Cologne, by birth a Dutchman. He died *ann.* 1554.

<https://archive.org/details/treatisescurvyt00lind/page/448/mode/2up>

The original in Latin:

“Ioannis Echthii De scorbuto, vel scorbutica passione epitome”, p.181-186.

<https://archive.org/details/descorbutotracta00senn/page/180/mode/2up>

https://www.google.com/books/edition/De_scorbuto_tractatus/W7w_AAAAcAAJ

https://www.google.com/books/edition/De_scorbuto_tractatus_Acc_ejusdem_argume/f2RWAAAACAAJ

A.D. 1541

Joan. Echthii de scorbuto, vel scorbutica passione, epitome.

p.355

He proposes it as a question, Whether the blood here may not be corrupted, without the spleen or any other of the *viscera* being affected? but is inclined to think the spleen often is. He assigns as causes of this disease, gross unwholsome food, of salt, dried, or putrid flesh and fish, pork, spoiled bread, stinking water, &c. He distinguishes the symptoms into two classes. The first contains such as appear at the beginning, and are common to it with other diseases; the second, the succeeding and more certain signs of the malady. Under the first, he comprehends a heaviness of the body, with a spontaneous lassitude, generally most sensibly felt after exercise; a tightness of the breast, and a weakness of the legs; an itching, redness, and pain of the gums; a change of colour in the face to a darkish hue: and observes, that where all these concur, we may foretel an approaching scurvy.

But the more immediate and certain signs he enumerates under the second class, viz. a fœtid breath, a spungy swelling of the gums, which are apt to bleed, with a loosening of the teeth; an eruption of leaden-coloured, purple, or livid spots, on the legs; or of somewhat broader speckled or dark-coloured *maculæ*, sometimes on the face, at other times on the legs. As the disease advances, the patients lose the use of their legs, and are

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subject to a difficulty of breathing, particularly when moved, or when they sit erect; at which times they are apt to faint: but upon being laid down again, they recover, and breathe freely; nay, when lying, they affirm that nothing ails them. But as they cannot always thus continue without some motion, they are subject to these perpetual swoons¹⁴. The appetite is seldom bad; on the contrary, they generally have a good one. There is sometimes observed an aggravation of the symptoms; with some on the fourth or fifth day, in others on the third. Some few have it every day, but without any fever: others become feverish. Preceding fevers may terminate critically, as it were, in the scurvy:

14 Swoon. Faint

and with such scurvies whole families and monasteries are together infected; which generally end either in a deadly dysentery, or, at other times, in a sudden and mortal faint. During the course of this disease, some are apt to be very costive¹⁵; while others have a continual *diarrhæa*. Sometimes their spotted legs swell so monstrously, as to resemble the *elephantiasis* of the *Arabians*; while others have them so extenuated, that the bones seem only covered with skin. The spots of some separate into black and duskish scales, like the *morphæa* and leprosy of the *Greeks*; while in others they remain soft, smooth, and shining; and the impression of the finger continues for some time upon the part. In those who die, the spots sometimes disappear; at other times they break out afresh. Lastly, there have been observed varicose swellings of the veins, as in those under the tongue, and of the lower lip.

He afterwards delivers the indications of cure, without giving us any remedies. And it may not be amiss to remark, that this is the first description now extant of the scurvy by a physician.

15 Costive. Constipated.